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MILESTONE REPORT

ML model selection and implementation plan

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ABSTRACT

Machine Learning (ML) techniques have been widely used both in science and industry for discovery purposes and prediction from data. The applications range from High Energy Physics experiments or biological studies to speech recognition or natural language processing and text analytics. Recently, ML methods are gaining interest in particle accelerator and beam diagnostics community. The project under task 10.6 aims to explore the potential of ML-based systems for identifying early signs of errant beam conditions in real-time. This document represents a technical report to be delivered at the milestone M48. It summarises the progress, status and future plans withing Task 10.6.

I.FAST Consortium, 2022

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1. Introduction

This document is a technical report related to the project under the I.FAST task 10.6 titled "Machine learning techniques for accelerator and target diagnostics". It summarises the status, and progress achieved during the time period from the start of the project (May 2021) to the month 18 of project execution (October 2022) and further plans. As such, it represents a technical report to be issued at milestone MS48 and reports on the efforts on the Machine Learning (ML) model selection and implementation plan.

The next subsection outlines the context and scope of the project. This is followed by a brief description of the European Spallation Source (ESS) linear accelerator (linac) and the beam instrumentation data relevant to this project. A list of progress points is briefly summarised at the end of this section. More details on the progress and further plans are given in the next two sections.

1.1 CONTEXT AND SCOPE

Rapid start-up and reliable operation of a particle accelerator requires a certain suite of beam instrumentation systems that are used for monitoring and characterisation of the beam. Accelerator failures are manifested through off-nominal beam states and subsequent beam losses that can lead to beam induced damage to the machine. Thus, in addition to monitoring, some of the beam instrumentation systems provide machine protection functionality by detecting potentially dangerous beam conditions and issuing a stop in beam production. The decision on when the beam conditions are dangerous can be derived offline with complex modelling through various simulations of beam dynamics, lost particles and thermomechanics. However, such an approach requires identification and rather detailed knowledge of all relevant failure scenarios. This can turn out to be a rather difficult task, particularly in linacs due to a large number possible failure scenarios.

Alternatively, ML techniques can learn from examples without requiring explicit rules or modelling. Thus, they offer a system-agnostic approach to detecting the onset of failures beforehand. Task 10.6, therefore, aims to explore the potential of low-latency ML techniques in order to improve performance and availability of high-power hadron accelerators with immediate application to the proton linac at the ESS [1][2] in Sweden. The idea is to apply ML predictive techniques to the large amount of data from various accelerator beam instrumentation systems and develop a data-driven model capable of identifying in real-time the early signs of beam conditions that can lead to beam induced damage or deterioration of the accelerator components if not mitigated. Such a model could then be utilised to process the measurements and assess the beam conditions in real-time as part of the data acquisition and processing path. Depending on the outcome of the assessment, a request for operator intervention or automated corrections may be issued. In severe cases, the beam production could be inhibited on an interpulse (<70 ms in case of ESS) or intrapulse (<2.86 ms in case of ESS) timescale. Thus, the ultimate objective of this project is to work out Machine Learning (ML) based

predictive models capable of protecting high-power linacs and suitable for implementation in a real-time platform.

The scope of this task covers:

- An assessment of predictive capabilities of several ML-based models evaluated with simulated and experimental beam instrumentation data. The latter includes ESS commissioning data anticipated within the time line of this project and potentially also existing data from the Spallation Neutron Source (SNS) in the USA.
- A prototype demonstration as a proof of principle. More specifically, this involves implementation of the most promising ML algorithm on a low-latency network of Field-programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) processing signals from an array of beam instrumentation detector channels.

As the main beneficiary, ESS is leading the task 10.6 and provides the accelerator and beam instrumentation systems as well as diagnostics, data analysis and FPGA-based expertise. Programming and implementation of the system is supported by Riga Technical University (RTU), Latvia, which offers ML and FPGA expertise. Additionally, Cosylab [3] is providing an FPGA specialist through a subcontract with ESS.

1.2 THE ESS LINAC AND RELEVANT BEAM INSTRUMENTATION

The ESS, which is currently being built in Lund, Sweden, will be a material science research facility. Once constructed, it will provide neutron beams for neutron-based research. The neutron production will be based on bombardment of a rotating tungsten target with a proton beam of 5 MW average power and macro-pulse beam current of 62.5 mA. A linac will accelerate protons to 2 GeV and transport them towards the target through a sequence of normal-conducting (NC) and superconducting (SC) accelerating structures (see Figure 1). The NC linac consists of an ion source, Low Energy Beam Transport (LEBT), Radio Frequency Quadrupole (RFQ), Medium Energy Beam Transport (MEBT) and Drift Tube Linac (DTL) sections. On the other hand, Spoke, Medium Beta and High Beta elliptical cavities together with High Energy Beta Transfer (HEBT) line comprise the SC linac.

The ESS linac is operated at 352.21 MHz and 704.42 MHz frequency in the initial and end parts, respectively. During neutron production beam is delivered to the target in 2.86 ms long macro-pulses with a repetition rate of 14 Hz, corresponding to a duty cycle of 4 %. Pulse length, repetition rate as well as macro-pulse beam current can during linac tuning and commissioning phases reach values below 5 μ s, 1 Hz and 6 mA, respectively.

Figure 1: Layout of the ESS linac. Red and blue colour mark the NC and SC parts of the linac, respectively

The ESS beam instrumentation systems that are planned to be included in this task are:

- **The Beam Current Monitoring (BCM)** system that monitors the charged particle beam current at several sensor locations. Additionally, this is the main diagnostic system used for machine protection purposes in the NC parts of the linac. There are 19 BCM sensors along the ESS linac **Error! Reference source not found.**[5][6].
- **The Beam Position Monitoring (BPM)** system that provides information on the longitudinal beam phase, horizontal/vertical position of the beam inside the vacuum chamber and the amplitude of one of the RF harmonics of the image current (first harmonics at the SCL and second in the NCL). There are 100 BPM systems along the ESS linac, and one of them is dedicated to high bandwidth measurements in the MEBT **Error! Reference source not found.**,[8][9].
- **The Beam Loss Monitoring (BLM)** system that provides information on the beam loss levels at each sensor location. Additionally, it is the main diagnostic system used for machine protection purposes in the SC parts of the linac. Two types of BLM systems differing in detector technology have been conceived at ESS. The neutron sensitive BLM (nBLM) [10],[9] system is based on 82 neutron detectors primarily covers the lower energy part of the ESS linac. Conversely, the Ionisation Chamber-based BLM (ICBLM) [11] system consists of 266 ionisation chambers located almost exclusively throughout the SC parts of the linac.
- **The Faraday Cup (FC)** that intercepts the beam and additionally provides information on the accumulated charge [12].

The ESS linac construction and commissioning is not completed yet and the next beam commissioning phase with beam to up to including DTL tank 4 is scheduled for Q2-Q3 2023. Hence, the beam instrumentation planned to be included in this project is limited to the one that covers linac up to including DTL tank 4. For the exact sensor layout along the linac parts relevant for this task see section 3.

The following lists the types of detailed processed data from these instrumentation systems that are relevant for this project:

- **BCM.** *Charge waveforms* over a time period of around 6 ms surrounding the 2.86 ms beam pulse with sample frequency of 5.50 MHz for each BCM sensor. These waveforms are processed from the raw data (sampled with 88 MHz) on the firmware (FW) level by applying correction algorithms (noise filtering, droop compensation, baseline correction).
- **BPM.** For each BPM system providing information on transversal and longitudinal beam properties, four waveforms over a time period of approximately $\pm 100 \mu\text{s}$ around the 2.86 ms

beam pulse window with an update rate of 5.87 MHz: *x coordinate*, *y coordinate*, *RF harmonics amplitude* and *beam phase*. These are calculated through the custom FPGA firmware, which is based on the near IQ-sampling algorithm [13]. The signal processing chain of the BPM allows the user to have access to 19 waveforms per BPM in each step of the DSP, such as

- Raw data waveforms from each individual antenna at a sampling rate of 88 MHz.
- Amplitude of the signal in each antenna and the sum of the amplitude of the 4 antennas at an update rate of 5.87 MHz.
- Horizontal and Vertical positions at an update rate of 5.87 MHz
- Phase of each antenna and the phase of the sum signal relative to the phase reference line.
- Phase reference line amplitude, phase and raw data.
- Average data within the Region Of Interest (ROI) window defined by the selected timing events are also delivered by the FPGA firmware for the SUM amplitude, phase and positions.

A high bandwidth BPM system is also available in the MEFT, which is dedicated for high bandwidth measurements. It measures the signal of the top stripline of a pair of BPMs in the MEFT for performing absolute beam energy measurements. Raw data is produced from the system during 3 ms of data and at a sampling rate of 6.4 GSPs and 3 GHz bandwidth. The system is generally used for absolute time-of-flight measurements and bunching structure characterization as well as timing alignment of the LEBT and MEFT Choppers.

- **ICBLM.** Continuous *current measurement* induced by the secondary particles traversing each detector. These data streams are sampled at 1MHz. They are extracted from the raw data on the FW-level by applying correction algorithms (background, modulation corrections). They correlate to the beam loss levels at the detector locations.
- **nBLM.** Continuous measurement of *neutrons per μ s* detected by each nBLM detector. These data streams are processed from the raw data on the FW-level by applying correction (pedestal, gain) and neutron detection algorithms.
- **FC.** Each Faraday Cup is supported by an acquisition similar to the BCM and as a result, provides similar data. Unlike the BCM, droop correction is not required.

1.3 PROGRESS SUMMARY

The following list summarises the current status and progress during the reporting period:

- During the ESS beam commissioning runs through July 2022, **data sets** have been acquired from most of the beam instrumentation in the first part of the ESS linac up to the DTL tank 1 (up to 21 MeV). This set of instrumentation covers the initial part of the suite planned to be used for the prototype (see section 3. and Figure 2. therein).
- A **doctoral student** from RTU has been engaged and has direct access to the data storage system. He is currently performing exploratory analysis on the data collected during the ESS beam commissioning run in June and July 2022.

- The work on producing **simulated data** of the ESS linac up to DTL tank 4 covering normal operation and anomalies has started. This data will be used to explore the sensitivity of a set of ML algorithms to diverse set of errant beam scenarios.
- To exchange relevant data and algorithms, a **collaboration with Oak Ridge National Lab** has been established and a memorandum of understanding has been drafted. ORNL is home of the SNS with a high power linac similar to the one at ESS. The SNS offers a more than a decade of operational date and has an active ML-related project.
- For data exchange, we agreed with SNS/ORNL on using the **HDF5-based NeXuS data** format standard [14], which is commonly used in neutron, x-ray and muon science communities. The initial data structures were defined for a few measurement types. These are planned to be refined and expanded in collaboration with ORNL and possibly SLAC and GSI as well.
- The **conceptual design** for the prototype demonstration of ML algorithm on a low-latency platform has been prepared. The core of this is an FPGA system fed by low-latency links from a set of instrumentation systems.
- In the laboratory, a prototype FPGA system (based on an Enclustra Development board) was demonstrated with the **XILINX software toolchain and generic ML algorithms**, see 3.4.3.
- The first version of the **low latency link** has been demonstrated by transporting waveforms with sub-microsecond latency at multigigabit per second rates.

The first and the last three points are further discussed in the sections 2. and 3. , respectively.

2. ML Model

This section focuses on the work on the ML model selection. First, applications of interest are outlined. This is followed by a description of example application. At the end of this section and overview of the plan with current status and future steps is given.

2.1 APPLICATIONS OF INTEREST

There are two specific low-latency applications that have been under consideration in the context of this project:

- ML-based Intelligent Trigger for Data-On-Demand (DoD) extraction and
- ML-based Machine Protection.

With the **ML-based Intelligent Trigger**, the idea is to have a FPGA hosting an ML-based model that is capable of identifying anomalies and thus distinguish *off-normal*, interesting events from the *normal* ones. Whenever an off-normal event is identified, a trigger for DoD acquisition is issued.

Here, DoD are defined as partially or fully processed, highly detailed data that are buffered and extracted from the FPGA level on certain event occurrence, hence on demand.

The major challenge foreseen with this application is connected to the fact that the accelerator conditions will change with time. Hence, if this is found to result in the need to re-train or worst case change the model too often for efficient operation of the system, unsupervised (on-line) ML learning model capable of coping with these changes may be required for this application.

One can divide ML algorithms roughly in to two categories: *supervised* and *unsupervised*, though the lines between them are often blurred [15]. The main difference between the two categories is that in the case of supervised learning, prior knowledge of the output values resulting from a given set of input samples is required. The goal of a supervised ML algorithm is then to learn the underlying function that best approximates the relation between the input samples and output values, which is achieved through offline training on a sample of input data with desired outputs. An unsupervised learning algorithm solves the task when only input data is available and its goal is to infer the underlying structure within a set of data points.

In the case of **ML-based machine protection**, the goal is to have a system that inhibits beam production whenever dangerous conditions are predicted. This application can be considered as a specific version of the Intelligent Trigger. Specifically, it is an Intelligent Trigger that has been trained to recognise damaging beam conditions. Whenever this is the case, the system then inhibits beam production and also triggers the DoD extraction. This DoD is called the Post-Mortem data, which is used in offline analysis to diagnose the problem that led to the beam production suppression.

For both of the applications, the instrumentation systems of interest are BLM, BPM and BCM systems.

2.2 EXAMPLE OF APPLICATION

Literature review has been carried out in order to gain an overview of the existing ML-based applications in the accelerator physics with emphasis on beam diagnostics and control. SNS has an ongoing project, where the focus is ML-based prediction and mitigation of failures due to errant beam condition in order to protect the SCL from the beam loss damage [16][17]. Their approach focuses on pulse-by-pulse prediction based on Differential Beam Current Monitor (DBCM) waveforms sampled at 100 MHz. These measurements include beam current at each sensor as well as the difference in the current measured by two BCM sensors at different locations along the linac. The difference measurement is the most direct characterization of the the beam loss levels between the two locations. The supervised ML algorithm is trained to label the data as good or bad. The former represents the normal operation data, while the latter labels the data that led to beam production suppression (beam trip). Several ML classifiers were tested, including k-Nearest neighbours, Logistic Regression, Gradient Boost, Neural Network etc, however, Random Forrest was found to be the optimal in terms of precision and speed.

The SNS linac produces 1 ms long beam pulses at rate of 60 Hz. Thus, the time available to make a prediction about the next pulse in case of the SNS linac is ~16 ms in contrast to ~68 ms at ESS.

A full pulse of DBCM and BCM data covers a time window of 1.2 ms (120 000 samples) around the beam. Extensive offline analysis on these data with a Random Forrest classifier has been performed [17]. The results show that the failure signature is imprinted already in the initial 1/4 of the pulse and is present in 4 pulses prior to the one that caused the beam trip. In addition to this, it was observed that the predictive power of using data from the DBCM or just one of the two BCMs was equally good. The actual trip prediction depends on the acceptable failure rate (False Positive rate). Requiring this to be ~0%, a True Positive rate of 58% and precision of 96% were achieved. Together with achieved classification time, which was found to be within 1 ms, the results offer a method applicable for real-time implementation. Random Forrest classification implementation on the FPGA is currently under test at SNS. Due to FPGA related limitations only part of the pulse (100us, 10 000 samples) is included in the classification.

2.3 STATUS AND FURTHER STEPS

The following list outlines the plan for this project:

- Project start (May 2021)
- Preparation (Q3 2021 - Q1 2022).
- ML model selection (Q1 2022 - Q2 2023).
- Milestone MS48: ML model selection and implementation plan, Technical report (October 2022).
- ML FPGA platform development (Q2 2021 - Q4 2022).
- Prototype demonstration (Q1 2023 - Q2 2024).
- Delivery 10.6: final technical report (February 2024).

The project started with a preparation phase focused on selecting application types, survey of existing relevant applications and data format preparation. We are now in the ML model selection phase, where the goal is to assess the predictive capabilities of a set of ML models by using

- experimental data from ESS and/or SNS and
- simulated data.

In parallel, the work on the ML FPGA platform development has started, where the focus is on low-latency network development and optimisation as well as acceleration of ML models on the selected FPGA platform. Current status of these efforts is discussed in more detail in the section 3. , while this section focuses on the work related to ML model selection. The project is concluded with a prototype demonstration in a laboratory set up or real environment.

As outlined in section 2.2, SNS has already demonstrated the capability of ML algorithms to predict the errant beam pulses based on the beam current measurement waveforms. Therefore, a collaboration

with SNS/ORNL has been established in order to be able share the knowledge and data. A series of discussions were held to assess the applicability of extended SNS example to ESS, where additional instrumentation waveforms are included.

Task 10.6 has one milestone (MS48) set for the end of October 2022, when this document is to be issued as a technical report. This milestone marks the completion of the initial assessment of the candidate ML-models by downselecting a few to be demonstrated on the low-latency platform. Due to changes in the ESS installation and beam commissioning schedule, the model selection is not completed yet. As outlined in the next subsections, this is expected to be completed before the next ESS beam commissioning run, scheduled for Q2-Q3 2023.

2.3.1 ESS experimental data

Measurements from BPM, BCM and partly also nBLM systems have been acquired during the last ESS beam commissioning run with beam to the end of DTL tank 1 (to 21 MeV), taking place during first half of July 2022. Current efforts are focused on data cleaning, where the goal is to extract stable run data from the archiving server by checking beam stability for each beam trip. If the condition for beam stability is satisfied for minimum 10 s prior to the trip, the data sets from relevant beam instrumentation is extracted to HDF5 files. The condition for beam stability is assumed to be satisfied, if certain average values characterising the beam current and position do not change significantly with time. Once the cleaning is completed, the focus will turn to offline analysis of this data. There are two types of studies that are planned to be performed: clustering and binary classification.

In the **clustering** study the aim is to try different ML models in order to explore whether the data can be grouped into clusters, such that each cluster can be connected to either normal operation or certain types of beam trips. Possible candidates for ML models to be tried here come from a class of Clustering algorithms [18], which rely on unsupervised classification.

The study with **binary classification** will be used to work out and assess the predictive capabilities of selected supervised models in same way as it has been performed at SNS. Thus, the set of likely candidate ML models to be tried here coincides with models that were most promising in the SNS analysis, for example, Random Forrest and Gradient Boosting. The goal of this study is to explore the predictive power and limitations of selected ML models. Specifically, the topic of interest includes

- Model dependence on the coverage along the linac: which minimum set of data channels gives adequate performance.
- Model dependence on the size, sampling rate and position (with respect to the cycle start) of the waveforms.

Depending on the results of these studies, most promising model in terms of speed, predictability and implementation limitations will be considered for prototype implementation of an Intelligent Trigger application. The next ESS beam commissioning run, which will cover beam to DTL tank 4, is scheduled for a 3-month period in Q2-Q3 2023. Dedicated stability runs, without active

commissioning activities, are planned to be performed during the initial part of this commissioning run. This data will then serve to exercise the selected models offline for final downselection to a few ML-models to be prototyped and implemented for testing in the laboratory setup. Additionally, we aim to test the prototype in the real environment as well, which is to take place towards the end of the commissioning run.

2.3.2 ESS simulation data

The work on simulation data has been initiated recently as well. The goal is to use this data to explore the sensitivity of ML models to different off-normal conditions. This toy data may not be most representative of the realistic failure scenarios. However, the idea is to understand what level of anomalies certain models are sensitive to and for which anomaly time scales they are most effective with the set of beam instrumentation planned to be used in the context of this project.

In order to produce such data, we are preparing OpenXAL [19] based simulations of the beam envelope under normal conditions and under anomalies in one parameter. OpenXAL is an open-source development environment written in Java for accelerator physics. It has been developed in a collaboration between many different accelerator facilities, ESS and SNS among them. On top of many services that OpenXAL can provide, a model for beam simulation is also available. The model treats only linear transfer matrices for the elements and use field-maps for the RF cavities; space-charge effects are also treated for continuous and bunched beam only in the linear approximation. The simulation in OpenXAL can be run via a Python API, rendering the task of running the simulation quick and easy. A large volume of data can be created quickly for a given section of the linac making it a great candidate for AI applications. Simulations of the ESS DTL 1 dynamics were already used to mimic data to be used to train a Neural Network (NN) based model that can determine the cavity settings (amplitude and phase) and input beam energy [20][21].

For the purpose of this project, OpenXAL will be used to create BPM, BCM and BLM data for unexpected events in the machine that may cause distortions on the waveforms read and processed by these instruments. A scan over a certain range of anomalies for selected parameters will be performed. The parameters of interest are phase for each cavity and Twiss parameters at the source. The former relates to radiofrequency (RF) cavity related faults, while the latter to faults related to the Ion Source. The two fault types are expected to be the cause for beam trips in majority of cases.

The anomalous processes of interest can have time scales ranging from intrapulse to several pulses. The results from static simulation scans will be used to construct failures with either intrapulse or pulse-to-pulse time dependence. In addition to model sensitivity studies, this type of toy data is planned to be used for testing the prototype in the laboratory environment.

3. Implementation and prototype plan

3.1 OVERVIEW

The second goal of this project is to run the selected algorithm with the lowest possible latency on live data from instrumentation suite. For this purpose, a prototype is under development, which is intended to be used in the lab and later installed at the ESS Linac to cover the ESS NCL parts, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: FPGA ML system overview. Lower layer: The schematic of the ESS linac as planned for 2022 commissioning run. Middle layer: The beam instrumentation acquisition systems that are providing the initial data sets, and the Machine Learning FPGA platform that is being prototyped. Top layer: Software tools and persistent data store

One of the most flexible solutions for running an ML based model with minimal latency is to use an FPGA, marked as the “ML FPGA system” in Figure 2. The already existing instrumentation systems have FPGA based acquisition cards with Small Form-factor Pluggable (SFP) transceivers prepared for connecting with optical fibres. Hence, the goal is to connect all of these systems to the ML FPGA system with the appropriate communication protocol.

The systems connected are:

- BCM: 8 sensors connected to one acquisition system.
- BPM: 20 sensors connected to three acquisition systems.
- nBLM: 36 sensors connected to two acquisition systems.
- ICBLM: 4 sensors connected to two acquisition systems.

In reality, there are different amounts of acquisition cards in the different systems. However, for the BPM systems, the data streams from the different cards can be concentrated to a single card within the system, such that only a single fiber needs to be connected to the ML FPGA system. This is not

possible for the BLM systems, thus, there is a need for another layer of FPGAs used just to combine and forward the data. This layer is marked with “optical combiner” in Figure 2.

3.2 ACQUISITION SYSTEM DATA

The systems themselves and the data they produce were introduced in section **Error! Reference source not found.**. This section focuses on how this data is transmitted on the optical links. There are still certain open questions around the difference between the data collected and the data transmitted across FPGAs, as the collected data is usually converted to human-readable format (Amperes, Voltages etc), while the lower level data is unformatted.

3.2.1 Beam Current Monitor (BCM)

The FPGA systems transmit this in its raw form as a 16-bit signed integer which is captured at 88 MSample/s. The window around the pulse is typically a bit more than the configured pulse length, so slightly more than 3ms. When there is no beam, the signal should be settling around zero, and this signal between pulses is also available.

The BCM system is connected to up to 8 sensors which implies rather high raw data bandwidth. There may be a need to decimate this waveform for bandwidth purposes.

3.2.2 Beam Position Monitor (BPM)

The X, Y and Phase waveforms are all downsampled by 15 from the 88 MSample/s base frequency, so each waveform is about ~5.8 MSample/s.

The X/Y positions in raw form are 16-bit signed integers and can be interpreted as a percentage value on how far off-center the beam is. It is typically multiplied with a sensor-specific factor to convert it to microns.

The raw phase value is harder to interpret as it is a fixed-point format with 3 integer bits and 12 fractional bits and together it represents the phase in radians from π to $-\pi$. This may be a problem since our captured data is usually converted into degrees.

3.2.3 Neutron sensitive Beam Loss Monitor (nBLM)

The neutron count is summarized for each 1 μ s window, hence, the raw data from an nBLM detector is a 32-bit unsigned integer at 1 MSample/s.

It is worth noting that like the BCM, the BLM systems are running continuously and data outside of the normal beam window might be interesting.

3.2.4 Ionisation Chamber-based BLM (ICBLM)

The Ionisation Chambers are connected to a transimpedance readout which measures the current in nA to mA ranges and is directly connected to an FPGA. To remove RF-induced gamma signals, this background is measured and subtracted from the input signal.

The background corrected waveforms are currently the candidate for input data to ML model. They are measured at 1 MSample/s and have 20-bits of precision, which is usually padded to a signed 32-bit integer.

3.3 ACQUISITION SYSTEM OPTICAL LINK SETUP

The existing acquisition systems are currently being updated to be able to support the bandwidth needs of the ML FPGA system. Each system has an FPGA with support to up to ~10 Gb/s transmission rates for each link, hence, roughly ~1250 MB/s.

3.3.1 Bandwidth analysis

Accelerator section	BCM			BPM			nBLM			ICBLM		
	Sensor	System	Bandwidth	Sensor	System	Bandwidth	Sensor	System	Bandwidth	Sensor	System	Bandwidth
ISrc/LEBT	2	BCM01	~1408 MB/s	-			-			-		
RFQ	1			-			-			-		
MEBT	1			7	BPM01	~328 MB/s	4	nBLM01 ¹	~72 MB/s	-		
DTL1	1			6	BPM02	~281 MB/s	8			1	ICBLM01*	~8 MB/s
DTL2	1			3	BPM03	~328 MB/s	8	nBLM01/02		1		
DTL3	1			2			8	nBLM02	~72 MB/s	1	ICBLM02*	~8 MB/s
DTL4	1			2			8			1		
Summary	8	1	~1408 MB/s	20	3	~937 MB/s	36	2	~144 MB/s	4	2	~16 MB/s

Table 1: Bandwidth summary of NCL Linac systems

The table summarizes the number of sensors/detectors that are connected to the beam instrumentation systems covering the NCL together with estimated bandwidth.

The calculations are as follows:

- BCM: The current waveform is 88 MSamples/s x 2bytes x 8 detectors = ~1408 MB/s
- BPM: The X/Y/Phase waveforms. Note, that the data is only interesting during the beam:
 - 5.8 MSamples/s x 2 bytes x 4 waveforms = ~ 47 MB/s per BPM
 - 3.5 ms beam window x 14 Hz (max rate) = ~47 MB/s * 0.049 = ~2.3 MB/s per BPM if optimized
- nBLM: neutron counts:
 - 1 MSample/s x 4 bytes = ~4 MB/s per detector
 - Each system has 18 detectors interleaved = 4 x 18 = ~72 MB/s per system
- icBLM: The background subtracted waveform is 1 MSample/s x 4 bytes x 2 detectors = ~8 MB/s

¹ In case of nBLM system, the detectors are interleaved across systems.

If required, there is some room for optimization.

The main conclusion from this is that it is not feasible to send the full raw BCM waveform across the optical links. Hence, we plan to evaluate if the decimated waveform would change the result in any significant way.

There are ongoing trials with BPM and BCM using a standard optical transmission protocol from Xilinx called Aurora. With the current laboratory solution, we have reached ~8 Gb/s and are working a slim protocol to identify which system the data comes from and support static multiplexing of the different sensors within the system onto the link.

3.4 ML FPGA ARCHITECTURE

The plan is to use the Xilinx methodology for machine learning on embedded systems.

Figure 3: Xilinx Tool flow for Machine learning on Zynq or Versal type FPGAs.

This means that the machine learning model is being run on specific accelerator elements in the FPGA. In the case of the Zynq this is Xilinx Deep Learning Processor cores (DPU) made in FPGA logic. For Versal there are already specific DPU cores for ML built into the chip for this purpose.

This should give us a lot of flexibility when it comes to trying different models or even running multiple models at the same time. The problem is that the latency may be larger than required,

however, especially in the case of Versal, once a specific model has been selected it can be optimized to fit the hardware to achieve very low latencies.

Initial evaluation has been done on the feasibility of using the Zynq platform (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

3.4.1 Versal ACAP platform

The first candidate is to build the prototype around a VCK190 Development board from Xilinx [22] that has already been ordered to support this task.

Figure 4: Versal VCK190 Development board.

The development board has 2 FMC+ slots plus several other connections for Ethernet, HDMI and USB etc. The board does not, however, have any general-purpose IO output other than through the FMC. The plan is to use the FMC slots for all of the external inputs and outputs. There are many vendors of SFP+ FMCs and at least one has support for stacking FMCs which means that we could have both a Quad SFP+ and a GPIO FMC in one of the slots. So the expected items would be:

- Quad SFP+ with feedthrough from Techway. See [23].
- Digital I/O that could connect to a timing receiver, for example from Creotech [24].

There are other options to consider as well as we could expose other types of FMCs with more SFP inputs for instance using QSFP (quad SFP) connectors and using splitter cables. However, these are not very flexible and would therefore restrict the connection topology. The system would also need a custom enclosure if we install it in a rack in the gallery.

Figure 5: Versal architecture overview.

The Versal Adaptive Compute Acceleration Platform (ACAP) is a new way of working when it comes to FPGA design. It is made up of FPGA logic regions interconnected with a re-programmable Network-on-Chip (NoC). This is part of the Vitis Platform methodology which means that part of the design is reconfigurable ("programmable") through software (SW). Hence, the design is split in two parts, shown as dashed lines in the Figure 5:

- **Hardware Platform:** Built out of "regular" VHDL and Xilinx block diagrams and IPs using the normal flow. The output for this is a definition that can be used in the Vitis SW flow.
- **Software Reconfigurable:** Processing "kernels" that can be either in PL or in the dedicated accelerators. The flow diagram (decides the NoC configuration) can be changed through SW.

The overview of the flow in the diagram is the following:

1. Waveforms and data from different systems are received over the optical links and are routed to the reconfigurable NoC.
2. The Optical input Decoding Kernels is high level synthesis code which takes the input stream from the optical links and reformats it into streams suitable for the AI kernels.
3. Optionally, the decoding kernels can write waveform data to the DDR memory for analysis and debugging.

4. The AI Kernels run the ML model inference on the waveform streams.
5. The AI Kernels' output is still to be determined. This part of the design is SW reconfigurable so the result could be sent both to DDR memory for visual inspection or as messages to the GPIO block to set output signals in case of interesting events or critical events.

The following sections describe the subcomponents in a bit more detail.

3.4.1.1 SFP+ FMC

This contains the code specific for the FMC. In this case we will have all the actual packet processing in a software reconfigurable part. Therefore, in the HDL part we will need 4 Xilinx Aurora IPs connected to the correct FMC pins and with the correct clocking setup to match the transmitters. To note is that the 4 IPs will be using the same clock source, which means that the 4 instances of Aurora will need to run at the same speed.

3.4.1.2 GPIO FMC

The FMC listed here has 5 programmable input/output ports. Not shown on the diagram in Figure 5 is that the GPIO block will have a register bank accessible from the CPU to make static setups, i.e. if a port is going to be used as input or as output. For now, it is assumed that we will send AXIS messages to set the output triggers high in case of an event. We foresee that:

- One pin is used for DoD instrument requests and could be connected to EVR TTL input.
- One or two pins are used for interlock and could be connected to the Fast Beam Interlock System (FBIS). FBIS handles the suppression of beam production once a request for beam inhibit is received.
- The rest of the pins could be used for Event Receiver (EVR) event inputs if we need to act on timing events.

3.4.1.3 NoC

The network-on-chip interconnect is a big reconfigurable interconnect structure, which is set up on device boot. The NoC supports multiple types of streams and can be used for both transporting address-requested items as well as statically routed streams of data. In our case we will utilize the statically routed streams to pass data from SFP+ FMC → decoding kernels → AI engines. One thing to note is that the NoC is not built of FPGA logic.

3.4.1.4 Optical Input Decoding Kernels

This logic is expected to be written as HLS and could in theory be moved to the SFP+ FMC hierarchy, but writing the logic in the SW reconfigurable region should provide flexibility. For now, these units are responsible for de-interleaving the data from the optical links. The details regarding the protocol are not finalised yet, but the assumption is that the data is separated into streams belonging to each

instrument. One option is to let each kernel have a Master AXI port to be able to reach main memory in which it could write the incoming data streams so we can verify that the data transferred is ok compared to the individual systems.

3.4.1.5 AI kernels

These are built in processing kernels from the ACAP. For more details on the hardware see [25]. How the ML model maps to the AI kernels and the efficiency will be part of the ML model integration.

3.4.2 Zynq based platform

One of the benefits of targeting a current generation platform is that we have it available in microTCA technology which is what we are using for all of our other acquisition systems. The most powerful platform we have available is the DAMC-FMC2ZUP from CAENels, see [26].

Figure 6: DAMC-FMC2ZUP FMC carrier acquisition card.

There are several technology benefits from this as the card is connected to the EVR card through the backplane links when plugged into a system. We also already have Rear-transition modules (RTM) that can be connected on the back-end of this card to interface with the FBIS system. Hence to support the current configuration all it needs is two FMC cards with SFP+ connectors.

Figure 7: DAMC FMC2ZUP FPGA Architecture

The Xilinx Zynq FPGA has support for using Deep-learning Processors (DPU) for AI inference. They are primarily made for acceleration, but can also be used for embedded ("edge") applications. There are some examples of this from Xilinx for mainly ML on camera applications. The main downside of this solution is that SW needs to be in the loop. This means that there needs to be a SW loop running on one of the real-time CPUs getting interrupted whenever there is enough data available to launch a job on the DPU cores. Consequently, this adds additional latency to the processing. The second downside is related to the format of the data. As we get multiple waveforms, we would like to store these in separate buffers, but the access scheme over many small buffers is not very memory efficient and would add additional latency. Therefore, the data needs to be packaged in a suitable format for the ML model to process on the DPUs. The overall flow in Figure 7 would be:

1. Waveforms and data from different systems are received over the optical links and are sent to the optical input decoding.
2. The input decoding sorts the input data from the different system and stores it in a suitable data-structure for the ML inference. This is then sent to a circular buffer in DDR memory.
3. When a suitable amount of data is stored in the circular buffer we start the ML model inference on the DPU.
4. The DPU result will need to be evaluated by SW and if an interesting event or dangerous condition is detected, a trigger is asserted via backplane IO. Thus, the ML model is driven by SW and scheduled to the DPU kernels.

The following sections describe the different parts in more details.

3.4.2.1 SFP+ FMC

Same setup as for the Versal above. See section 3.4.1.1.

3.4.2.2 Optical input decoding

This unit has 8 AXI streaming inputs from the optical links. It decodes the incoming data of interleaved data from the different systems. It would have two purposes. First would be to format the data into chunks of data that the ML model can handle. The assumption is that we make a data structure containing 1 μ s of data from all of the connected systems. Each chunk is stored in a circular buffer using an AXI data mover unit. This unit may need to be reworked when we have more details of how the ML model executes.

A secondary feature would be debug monitoring, i.e. have a number of ESS developed axis2maxi components (AXI stream to Master AXI) to be able to store incoming waveforms into memory. This can be used to compare the waveforms on the ML FPGA versus the acquisition system to verify that data is transported as expected.

3.4.2.3 DPU and AXI interconnect

This will be made using the "Vitis Embedded platform" for Zynq. This is based around the guideline in [27]. This means we create the AXI interconnect and interrupts and leave them unconnected. Thus, the rest of the FPGA is tiled into slots where DPU kernels (or other acceleration kernels) can be instantiated. This means that the Vitis SW flow can be used to develop the ML model and assign it to the platform DPUs. This flow has been tested on another Zynq platform – for more detail see section 3.4.3.

3.4.2.4 Backplane IO

SW registers route backplane triggers towards the EVR. This would be used to send an instrument trigger when the ML model detects an interesting condition or if needed to synchronize events within the distributed system.

3.4.2.5 RTM IO

For this, a standard RTM is used to connect to the FBIS. Basically, we could interrupt the beam production by dropping the beam permit signal upon detection of a damaging condition.

3.4.3 Tool flow evaluation

Because of the world-wide supply chain issues, we could not get our hands any real hardware until recently. Therefore, the tool trials were performed on an older prototype platform equipped with a Zynq MPSoC FPGA similar to that of the FMC2ZUP platform.

The tool trials were performed to be able get a feeling for how complex it is to work with the Zynq MPSoC DPU.

The following hardware was used:

- Enclustra Mercury XU1 module (ID: ME-XU1-15EG-2I-D12E)
- Enclustra Mercury PE1 base board (PCIe dev board)

Figure 8: Enclustra XU1 + PE1 development board.

As mentioned earlier, the Zynq MPSoC is a combination of CPU and FPGA logic. It is connected with the network outlet seen in on Figure 8 and runs an embedded version of Petalinux. The following tool versions were evaluated:

- Xilinx Vivado 2020.2
- Xilinx Petalinux SDK 2020.2
- Xilinx Vitis-AI libraries 1.3.2

The setup follows the guidelines from Xilinx [27], but are modified to fit the Enclustra board platform.

This is a brief summary of what has been set up. From Figure 3 this would be what the HW/SW developer would set up so that a user could deploy a ML model on the system.

The system was configured to have 2 Deep Learning Processor units (DPU) running at a 600 MHz DSP frequency and 300 MHz core frequency with the B4096 architecture. This architecture is made

for large convolutional networks and with an optimized model running 4096 multiply and accumulate operation per cycle. Of course, the efficiency depends on the model. This results in a theoretical GOPs performance of about 2457 which is about the same as a low-end graphics card of today, but with the benefits of being much more tightly coupled to the input data and providing a much tighter SW stack.

Petalinux was configured to include the Vitis-AI packages as well as many of the common development tools needed to play around with the system, including Jupyter lab.

Figure 9: Example of running Jupyterlab ML example on Zynq DPU.

Figure 9 shows an example of how a job is deployed to run the ML inference, in this case a resnet50 model with an image set containing a wide variety of different images, with some random images selected based on what the network can identify. The images are resized in python to fit the network (224x224).

The example above is only running a single thread on a single core – it runs at about 90 fps using 2 threads and 2 cores. The results are in line with what is presented in [27], listed under ZCU104 FPGA results.

With delayed ESS beam commissioning schedule, there has not been any opportunity to evaluate a real model developed for accelerator data. However, speculating based on the results thus far, one could probably run a rather large model over 70 ms and detect anomalies before the next pulse. However, achieving a latency low enough to that stop beam within the pulse will require much more optimization effort.

4. Summary

Task 10.6 aims to explore the applicability of ML-based models to high power hadron accelerators. More specifically, algorithms for intelligent triggering and machine protection functions are being evaluated.

A collaboration with SNS/ORNL has been established in order to share data and knowledge. SNS has a more than a decade of operational experience with a linac similar to the one at ESS. In addition to this, they have an active ML-based project, where they already demonstrated the applicability of ML techniques to errant beam prediction. For data exchange, an agreement was reached to use an HDF5-based NeXuS data format standard common in neutron, X-ray and muon science communities.

Within the frame of task 10.6, ML-algorithms are planned to be demonstrated on a low-latency platform. As discussed in section 3. , the conceptual design of such a prototype had been prepared. The core of this architecture is an FPGA system fed by low-latency links from multiple instrumentation systems. In the laboratory, a prototype FPGA system (based on a Enclustra development board) was demonstrated with the XILINX software toolchain and generic ML algorithms. The first version of the low latency link was also demonstrated by transporting waveforms with sub-microsecond latency at multigigabit per second rates.

During the last beam commissioning run at ESS, with beam through DTL tank 1, most data sets from beam instrumentation relevant for this project have been acquired. Offline analysis is currently ongoing, where the aim is to prepare the analysis tools, explore the predictive power and limitations of several ML algorithms and select one or a few for further use. These will be applied in offline analysis during the next beam commissioning run scheduled for Q2-Q3 2023, when full set of beam instrumentation planned for the prototype demonstration will be used. The model with best performance in terms of speed and predictability will then be selected for implementation on the low-latency platform, and then tested first in laboratory and then in the realistic environment of the ESS linac.

Toy data are currently being prepared. They are extracted from beam envelope simulations of normal and faulty conditions. This toy data is to be used in exploratory analysis addressing the sensitivity of selected ML algorithms to errant conditions. The same type of data is planned to be used to test the prototype implementation in a controlled laboratory environment.

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